

Research Article

Using blockchain to signal quality in the food supply chain: The impact on consumer purchase intentions and the moderating effect of brand familiarity

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ABSTRACT

Food safety is a public health issue of paramount importance. In this regard, blockchain has emerged as a promising technology that allows users to effectively and efficiently record the origin and flow of products and eliminate or reduce harmful food fraud. Consumers can benefit from this development by receiving up-to-date and verifiable information about the origins and delivery routes of their purchases. Drawing on signaling theory and the results of two experimental studies with 151 and 152 participants, respectively, we investigate how the use of blockchain to trace food products impacts consumers' perception of product quality as a mediating variable and subsequently their purchase intention. Our framework further considers brand familiarity as a moderating variable. The findings from the two experiments show that blockchain labels as a signaling mechanism in food supply chains help to strengthen consumers' perceived quality of food products, which, in turn, increases their purchase intention. This effect is more pronounced for less familiar brands, which is valuable information for managers who want to build a brand's reputation. From an academic perspective, we highlight the applicability of signaling theory to identify blockchain-based traceability systems as important drivers of perceived product quality and consequently purchase intention.

1. Introduction

The safety and quality of food products has become a worldwide matter of paramount importance. An estimated 420,000 people die each year after consuming contaminated food and a further 600 million become ill (World Health Organization, 2019). In 40% of these cases, children under five years of age are affected, which leads to 125,000 deaths annually. The World Health Organization (WHO) concludes that foodborne diseases impede socioeconomic development and harm national economies, tourism, and trade. Highly publicized food safety incidents, such as tainted milk in China, mad cow disease in Britain, E.coli infected cucumber in Germany, or peanut butter infected with bacteria in the U.S. (Lethbridge, 2018) have raised substantial public interest in food traceability, which is defined as "the ability to track any food, feed, food-producing animal or substance that will be used for consumption, through all stages of production, processing, and distribution" (European Commission, 2007, p. 1). Reliable tracing of food products can also help to mitigate incidents of food fraud, the total worldwide cost of

which amounts to an alarming \$30 to \$40 billion per year (Storey, 2020). Among the most affected food categories are olive oil (substitution with low-cost alternatives), seafood (cheap fish misrepresented as high-value fish), milk-based products (laced with powders, watered down, supplemented with melamine), honey (added syrup, fructose, glucose), and fruit juices (watered down, added dye and flavorings).

As a potential remedy for the current situation, the WHO suggests that governments, producers, and consumers work together to ensure food safety (World Health Organization, 2019), which necessitates the distribution of relevant information throughout intricate food value networks. Consequently, it is in the interest of profit-oriented companies to apply information systems for tracing food products, which, as an important side effect, can also result in increased profitability (Regattieri, Gamberi, & Manzini, 2007). Informing consumers about the origin and transportation of their products reduces information asymmetries and can help to reduce health risks (Yoo, Parameswaran, & Kishore, 2015). This increased transparency can help consumers to better assess the qualities of a specific product.

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Previous literature has already suggested that blockchain's features of immutability and shared data access among supply chain participants can play an important role in achieving information transparency along the supply chain (Rogerson & Parry, 2020). The question remains, however, how this information can be conveyed efficiently to the final consumers and to what extent it actually impacts their perceptions and behavioral intentions. It is reasonable to assume that – as is the case with all modern technologies – consumers need to be educated on the benefits of this new technology. Similarly, a growing number of articles in high-profile newspapers, such as *The New York Times*, *Harvard Business Review*, and the *Financial Times*, inform consumers about the advantages of blockchain-based traceability systems (Corkery & Popper, 2018; Vincent, 2021; Vitasek, Bayliss, Owen, & Srivastava, 2022). Nevertheless, until a mutual understanding of blockchain technology is reached, companies who want to use blockchain as a quality signal for their products are well advised to briefly inform customers of its advantages. In support of this notion, a study confirms that the quality signaling of sustainability labels can be enhanced by increasing consumers' understanding about what the label conveys (Samant & Seo, 2016). In order to address this research gap, we pose the following research questions:

RQ1. : How can traceability labels signaling the use of blockchain technology impact consumers' perceptions of product quality and their purchase intentions?

RQ2. : What role does brand familiarity play in consumers' perception of blockchain-enhanced product quality?

In order to answer these research questions, we apply signaling theory and test a model that incorporates the positive influence of traceability systems on perceived product quality. This, in turn, is predicted to result in increased purchase intention. More specifically, our model postulates that a blockchain-based decentralized information system has a superior impact on consumers' product quality perceptions as compared to a traditional centralized traceability system. We include brand familiarity, which can be defined as consumers' awareness of a specific brand and its characteristics (Baker, Hutchinson, Moore, & Nedungadi, 1986), as a variable that moderates the effect of the traceability label on perceived product quality. The latter can be defined as a "consumer's judgment about a product's overall excellence or superiority" (Zeithaml, 1988, p. 3). The postulated effects are tested with two experiments involving consumers and using different stimuli.

This paper is structured as follows: In Section 2 we discuss the relevant literature, starting with signaling theory, which provides the theoretical background for our study, and then elaborating on blockchain-based traceability systems that can help companies to better oversee and coordinate their supply chains. In Section 3 we develop our hypotheses and combine them into a theoretical model that integrates the effect of labels on perceived product quality and purchase intention with brand familiarity as a moderating variable. We conducted two empirical survey studies with consumers that are discussed in detail in Section 4, followed by a discussion of the findings and their implications for practitioners and academics in Section 5. We conclude the paper in Section 6 by outlining the key points that emerged from this research.

2. Literature review

2.1. Signaling theory

Individuals need information to make decisions in various contexts, whether in private households, governments, or businesses (Connelly, Certo, Ireland, & Reutzel, 2011). When the parties involved in decision-making do not possess the same amount and quality of information, as is frequently the case, information asymmetry occurs (Stiglitz, 2002). Signaling theory (or signal theory) explores how information asymmetries between two parties can be reduced (Spence, 1973). More specifically, it describes "how actors selecting among a

choice set can successfully make determinations about the unobservable quality of their selection via observable signals" (Connelly, 2016, p. 745). Signaling theory was initially developed in the context of job markets wherein employers lack essential information about applicants. Applicants try to compensate for this information shortage by providing signals in the form of educational achievements (Spence, 2002). Information asymmetries are not restricted to the labor market, however, but also occur in consumer good markets. For example, Stiglitz (2002) emphasizes the relevance of information asymmetry in assessing a product's quality. This is illustrated by car sellers who offer warranties to not only reduce consumers' perceived risk but also to signal the high quality of their products. Consumers therefore compensate for a lack of substantive information with inferential information: namely the generation of if-then linkages between information given through signals and conclusions (Kardes, Posavac, & Cronley, 2004; Kruglanski & Webster, 1996; Pee, Jiang, & Klein, 2018).

In situations of considerable information asymmetry, signals such as logos, labels, and high quality descriptions (Singh & Sirdeshmukh, 2000) serve as tools to deliver information to potential customers (Akdeniz & Talay, 2013) so that they can infer quality (Grunert, 2005) and differentiate between high and low quality sellers (Boulding & Kirmani, 1993; Mavlanova, Benbunan-Fich, & Koufaris, 2012). Online retailers, for example, frequently make strategic use of signals, such as website features, to carry information from sellers to buyers (Mavlanova et al., 2012). Despite such efforts, problems of information asymmetry between buyers and sellers persist in numerous markets as a result of information uncertainties pertaining to both product-based and seller-based information. Furthermore, information asymmetry can persist despite the presence of signaling mechanisms including reputation feedback and the disclosure of product conditions (Ghose, 2009). This can be attributed to the fact that information can easily be faked or biased (Cao, 2019). A market that is particularly prone to fraud is the food market, which is regularly affected by scandals that not only erode consumers' confidence but might even have detrimental effects on their personal health and wellbeing (Lethbridge, 2018).

Signaling theory in combination with blockchain has been previously used to explain dynamics of initial coin offerings (ICOs) through the signaling of ventures' technological capabilities (Fisch, 2019). Another example stems from Chod, Trichakis, Tsoukalas, Aspegren, and Weber (2018) who illustrate that it is more efficient for firms to signal their fundamental quality to lenders through inventory transactions rather than loan requests and that blockchain outperforms traditional monitoring mechanisms in that matter.

It has the potential to remedy this situation by allowing timely access to verifiable information that is shared between numerous network participants. In order to better understand whether this can impact consumers' attitudes and intentions, the perception of the technology and its implications need to be explored. Therefore, we investigate whether signaling the use of blockchain-based information can impact consumers' purchase intentions and the influence of brand familiarity in the following sections.

2.2. Blockchain-based traceability systems

Food traceability is defined as "the ability to track any food, feed, food-producing animal, or substance that will be used for consumption, through all stages of production, processing, and distribution" (European Commission, 2007, p. 1). Blockchain technology has features that can positively impact various industries (Ali, Ally, Clutterbuck & Dwivedi, 2020; Beck, Avital, Rossi & Thatcher, 2017; Frizzo-Barker, Chow-White, Adams, Mentanko, Ha & Green, 2020; Iansiti & Lakhani, 2017; Rana et al., 2021) and especially transform supply chains (Montecchi, Planger, & Etter, 2019; Treiblmaier, 2018). Blockchain can be defined as "a digital, decentralized, and distributed ledger in which transactions are logged and added in chronological order with the goal of creating permanent and tamper-proof records" (Treiblmaier, 2018, p.

547). This technology did not come out of the blue but rather builds on previous work related to linked timestamping, digital cash, proof of work, byzantine fault tolerance, asymmetric cryptography, and smart contracts (Narayanan & Clark, 2017). All of these key ideas were cleverly combined by a pseudonymous author in the Bitcoin protocol, which finally solved the problem of double spending, meaning the spending of a digital token more than once (Nakamoto, 2008). Given these features, blockchain technology makes it possible to use the internet as a medium for the exchange of value rather than solely for communication or social interaction purposes. At its core, blockchain is a peer-to-peer network that uses elaborate consensus mechanisms to keep records of digital assets in a decentralized nature (Beck, Müller-Bloch, & King, 2018; Lacity, 2018). Used in a supply chain, for example, this feature differentiates blockchain from traditional databases, which are centrally controlled. Blockchain can potentially eliminate or at least mitigate numerous sources of risk, including preventing risk occurrence, reducing the impact of supply chain disruptions, improving companies' flexibility in dealing with supply chain disruptions, and changing business-as-usual attitudes (Min, 2019).

In order to stay profitable in a highly competitive environment, retailers need to closely work together with suppliers, which includes sharing detailed information regarding the origin and transportation of products (Ganesan, George, Jap, Palmatier, & Weitz, 2009; Treiblmaier, Mirkovski, Lowry, & Zacharia, 2020). Improved communication with their customers can help companies in the food sector to increase their competitiveness (Busby, 2019), whereas a lack of information sharing can have detrimental effects and cause concerns among consumers related to the quality of food (McEachern & Seaman, 2005).

The combination of data immutability and the distribution among numerous nodes, each of which shares an identical copy of all recorded transactions, enables a level of traceability that was not possible prior to the emergence of blockchain. Once stored, data can hardly be modified and any attempt to do so can be relatively easily detected. Furthermore, while by no means perfect, blockchain has been shown to be relatively resistant to hacking, and it is the combination of all these characteristics that can potentially create solutions to foster supply chain resilience (Min, 2019; Treiblmaier, 2019).

Despite the benefits associated with a blockchain-based traceability system as outlined in the extant literature, little is known about factors that prompt blockchain implementation in supply chains. As an exception, a recent study confirms that traceability represents the major determinant for blockchain adoption in the agriculture supply chain (Kamble, Gunasekaran, & Sharma, 2020). Likewise, Centobelli, Cerchione, Vecchio, Oropallo, and Secundo (2021) note that the three factors of trust, traceability, and transparency determine blockchain platform adoption in a supply chain context. Previous research has confirmed that its application can improve the transparency and traceability of supply chains and also improve the amount of swift trust occurring in temporary organizational structures (Dubey, Gunasekaran, Bryde, Dwivedi, & Papadopoulos, 2020). From a profit maximization perspective, research clearly recommends the adoption of blockchain for products with high traceability awareness (i.e., concerns about a product's safety and quality) while retailers are simultaneously encouraged to convey the advantages of blockchain in their marketing communication strategies (Fan, Wu, & Cao, 2022). As a consequence, the trust in a given organization increases. The following section elaborates on how the adoption of a blockchain-based supply chain management system can be used to signal product quality to consumers.

3. Hypotheses development and conceptual research framework

Information about a product's provenance, such as its origin, authenticity, integrity, and custody, assures customers of their purchasing decisions. Blockchain can help to establish each of these by enabling traceability, certifiability, trackability, and verifiability (Montecchi et al., 2019). On a theoretical level, Yiannas (2018)

illustrated how blockchain technology can enhance food traceability and transparency. Corroborating the findings of academic research, real-world evidence confirms the potential of blockchain in food traceability systems, as well-known food retailers have already started implementing blockchain-based systems. In September 2018, Walmart publicly announced the tracking of lettuce using Blockchain technology in response to contaminated romaine lettuce (Corkery & Popper, 2018). Likewise, Europe's largest retailer, Carrefour, has deployed the technology to track chickens, eggs, and tomatoes to protect against salmonella contamination (Reuters, 2018). The announcement and publication of company statements in prominent outlets such as the New York Times and Reuters underscores how important it is for companies to publicly communicate their efforts to deploy technology for ensuring food safety.

This combination of a sound theoretical foundation and functional real-world examples strongly suggests that blockchain is a promising technology to ensure traceability, hence food quality and safety, throughout the whole supply chain. Drawing on signaling theory (Connelly, 2016), we propose that traceability labels increase purchase intentions for food products. We further propose that this effect is mediated by product quality perceptions. Traceability and quality labels likely serve as cues that help consumers to reduce information asymmetry in terms of product quality (Bonnet, Hilger, & Villas-Boas, 2020; Spence, 2002; Stiglitz, 2000). However, the positive influence of traceability on product quality perceptions is also assumed to vary depending on the product's familiarity (Janiszewski & Van Osselaer, 2000). Familiar brands are usually associated with a specific quality, hence additional signals might not cause an increase in perceived quality due to ceiling effects (Simonin & Ruth, 1998). In the following section we discuss the respective hypotheses in more detail.

3.1. The relationship between blockchain-based traceability systems and purchase intentions

To establish consumer confidence in product quality, retailers must clearly communicate their efforts. Labeling is a particularly useful means of signaling product quality. For instance, recent research demonstrates that a sustainability label is the third most important attribute for product choice, which is explained by the quality signaling effect (Sigurdsson et al., 2022). This result verifies prior research, which confirms that consumers often use product labeling as a basis for their buying decisions (Berry, Mukherjee, Burton, & Howlett, 2015) and that sustainability and food quality labels can increase purchase intentions (Silva, de, Biotto, Efraim, & Queiroz, 2017). Likewise, prior research has confirmed that traceability labels can increase consumers' purchase intentions (Lee, Bae, & Kim, 2020).

As a credence attribute, food traceability is typically hard for consumers to verify and is therefore associated with higher risk as compared to search and experience attributes (Darby & Karni, 1973; Mitra, Reiss, & Capella, 1999; Sharma, Sivakumaran, & Marshall, 2014). In this regard, extant research acknowledges the potential of food traceability systems to increase consumers' purchase intentions. For example, Chen and Huang (2013) have found that food traceability systems can help to reduce uncertainty caused by information asymmetry and fears of seller opportunism among consumers. This, in turn, increases their purchase intentions for fast food (Chen & Huang, 2013). Similarly, QR-based traceability labels have a positive influence on consumers' attitudes toward beef products and increases purchase intentions (Spence, Stancu, Elliott, & Dean, 2018). In addition, the inclusion of objectifiable information can strengthen the positive influence of labels on consumers' responses (Berry et al., 2015). In summary, prior studies acknowledge the positive impacts of traceability labels on behavioral intentions, which has mainly been explained by the reduction of information asymmetry and a signal of product quality. Additionally, the credibility of labels determines their positive effects (Brach, Walsh, & Shaw, 2018). The authors demonstrate that a third-party sustainability label reduces

perceived financial and performance risk to a greater extent as compared to a label issued by a private organization. Likewise, green labels are perceived as being more credible when issued by a third party (D'Souza, Taghian, Lamb, & Peretiatko, 2007).

In this regard, blockchain technology adds an additional layer of credibility, which has also been confirmed by studies from consulting companies, such as KPMG (Paquette & Wieger, 2021) and McKinsey (Galea-Pace, 2020). Its decentralized nature implies that no entity can delete a previously stored piece of information against the will of the majority (Min, 2019). This, in turn, can support the enforcement of sustainability-related standards (Kshetri, 2021).

Thus, we hypothesize:

H1. : A blockchain-based traceability label increases purchase intentions.

3.2. The mediating role of product quality perceptions

Signs and logos are often used to convey sellers' identity attributes. However, consumers frequently base their product choices not only on the sellers' descriptions but also on product-specific credence information such as information about a given product's origin, processing, or production information (Fernqvist & Ekelund, 2014). These credence attributes are used to infer the quality of products (Samant & Seo, 2016; Yang, Renwick, Tantiwat, Revoredo-Giha, & Wu, 2021). Emphasizing the relevance of quality labels and their function to protect and promote a product's unique characteristics, the European Commission provides a comprehensive database on established quality labels for perishable food products (European Commission, 2022).

Consumers' perceptions of food products also depend on their assessment of whether the products can fulfill various functional goals, such as improving well-being (Andrews, Netemeyer, & Burton, 1998). In this regard, verbal food descriptions influence consumers' perceptions of food and help them to develop food preferences (Blackburn, Yilmaz, & Boyd, 2018). In a similar vein, confidence in brand origin identification positively influences brand value evaluations. Additionally, front-of-package labeling has been found to be an effective means of aiding consumers in identifying healthier products (Ikonen, Sotgiu, Aydinli, & Verlegh, 2020). (Zhou, Yang, & Hui, 2010) as well as more sustainable products (Samant & Seo, 2016). In addition to quality and safety standards, sustainability aspects have been identified as an important aspect of traceability systems (Gallo, Accorsi, Goh, Hsiao, & Manzini, 2021). Indeed, research conducted by the Boston Consulting group in 2013 confirms the growth potential of responsible consumption brands; the annual growth of responsible consumption brands doubled as compared to non-responsible consumption brands in 2013 alone (Smits, Vismans, van Zon, & Wood, 2015). This trend is still ongoing, and every fourth consumer indicates paying attention to sustainable consumption and pro-environmental shopping behavior (Gatzer & Magnin, 2021).

Numerous constructs have been suggested in the IS literature as antecedents of purchase intention, including several informational (e.g., reviews, trustworthiness) and normative (e.g., recommendations, service popularity) influences. More specifically, Tsiotsou (2006) and Wells, Valacich, and Hess (2011) investigated the relationship between perceived product quality and purchase intention in an online environment. They found the relationship between product quality perceptions and online purchase intentions to be consistently significant across a series of three studies using undergraduate students (Wells et al., 2011). A more recent study reveals that, in the context of olive oil, product labeling (origin and organic labels) positively impacts purchase intention by prompting favorable quality associations (Spognardi, Vistocco, Cappelli, & Papetti, 2021). Building on previous research, we therefore assume that labels impact consumers' product quality perceptions and subsequently their purchase intentions, and hypothesize:

H2. : The positive effect of a blockchain-based traceability label on purchase intention is mediated through perceived product quality.

3.3. The moderating effects of brand familiarity

The outcome of a brand adding a label depends on the strength of the label and the strength of the brand. Brand strength usually correlates with brand familiarity, such that more familiar brands possess higher brand strength (Simonin & Ruth, 1998). However, the effect of branding is not always straightforward. For example, empirical evidence suggests that using a strong brand to promote a charity cause does not improve its brand equity (Lafferty, Goldsmith, & Hult, 2004), but a positive effect is present for brands of moderate strength. Likewise, research indicates the absence of any additional effect for brand alliances constituted by two already strong brands (Besharat, 2010; Venkatesh & Mahajan, 1997). Ceiling effects represent the theoretical explanation for the absence of a contribution by a main brand on the co-brand (Simonin & Ruth, 1998). Analogues to brands in a co-branding arrangement, labels reflect signals and work as cues that stimulate varied associations (Carpenter & Larceneux, 2008). A strong brand is clearly associated with a favorable impression (e.g., of product quality); hence, no value may be added by the label (Janiszewski & Van Osselaer, 2000). Conversely, consumers' perceptions of an unknown brand can be shaped more easily by adding a label.

Further, extant literature reveals that the signaling effect of an organic label on product quality perceptions depends on the brand's equity level (Larceneux, Benoit-Moreau, & Renaudin, 2012). Given the superior qualities of blockchain in terms of informational quality and its resistance to hacking, we assume that a blockchain label represents a strong cue for signaling product quality. We further propose that adding a blockchain label to a familiar (i.e., strong) brand does not increase product quality perceptions due to the aforementioned ceiling effects. Having already achieved highly positive product quality perceptions through a familiar brand, no further associative learning in terms of product quality is possible when adding a blockchain label. In contrast, adding a blockchain label to a less familiar brand enables associative learning. This reasoning suggests that:

H3. : Brand familiarity moderates the indirect effect of a blockchain-based traceability label on purchase intention, so that the mediating effect is stronger for less familiar brands (as compared to familiar brands).

Fig. 1 summarizes the three hypotheses in a theoretical model.

4. Research design

We test the theoretical model, as shown in Fig. 1, in two consecutive experiments. We preferred an experimental design over a quasi-experimental design or a purely correlational study since experiments are usually considered to be the best way to identify causal relations. Furthermore, the randomization process helps to equate groups on expectations of every variable before treatment, whether observed or not, and yields unbiased estimates of the average treatment effect (Shadish, Cook, & Campbell, 2001). In study 1, we relied on a convenience sample (N = 151) to test the positive influence of traceability labeling on purchase intention (H1) in the food category "honey", which is a product that is frequently adulterated by diverse types of cheap sugar solutions, such as corn syrup or fructose syrup. We also examine the mediating effect of perceived product quality on the influence of traceability labeling on purchase intention by estimating a mediation model in the SPSS PROCESS macro (H2). Study 2 replicates study 1 in a different food category, salmon, which has been labeled as "the most toxic food in the world" (Mercola, 2018). Data from 152 respondents collected via an online experiment was analyzed by means of moderated mediation analysis. In both studies, the respondents were briefly informed about those blockchain properties that can potentially impact supply chain traceability. Expanding the investigations in study 1, study 2 also assesses whether a moderating effect of brand familiarity impacts the mediating role of perceived product quality on purchase intention (H3).

Fig. 1. Proposed theoretical model and hypotheses.

4.1. Study 1 The influence of a blockchain-based traceability label on purchase intention

4.1.1. Design, procedure, and sample

The first study was designed to test the direct effect of traceability labeling on purchase intention (H1) as well as the mediating effect of perceived product quality on the influence of traceability on purchase intention (H2). In this experiment, we used a one-factor between-subjects design with traceability labeling as the manipulated variable. We included a no-label condition as the control group and a blockchain-based traceability label as the experimental group. In the no-label condition, the brand was displayed without any manipulation or amendments to its original appearance. In the blockchain-based traceability labeling condition, a fictitious label was created stating “Blockchain Tracking” and “Source verified” (see Fig. 2).

The experiment was conducted online, and the target population was consumers. Students of a marketing research class were asked to acquire a convenience sample by forwarding the link to the online experiment to their family members, friends, and colleagues in return for course credits. Each student was asked to acquire at least 25 participants. The data was collected in April 2019.

Particular effort was devoted to avoiding a student sample and instead acquiring a diverse sample characterized by different ages, genders, and educational backgrounds. Furthermore, we advised students to only send out the questionnaire to people who usually purchase that specific type of product, which eliminated the confounding effect of asking vegetarians whether they would like to buy fish, for example. Since the research focus is on basic psychological processes which are

independent of sample characteristics, the reliance on a convenience sample is well justified (Kardes, 1996). Furthermore, convenience sampling procedures are widely accepted in academic research (Peterson & Merunka, 2014). Finally, all further analyses are correlational instead of descriptive, which further reduces the effect of a potential sample bias (Blair & Zinkhan, 2006).

Recent news articles that discuss fraudulent food practices guided the selection of brands for stimulus material (e.g., The Economist, 2018). Among others, honey has routinely been included among the most product categories associated with fraud (Coronel-Gavro, Yagüe-Jiménez, & Blanco-Murillo, 2021), which is often a result of food adulteration with jaggery or sugar syrup (World Health Organization, 2015). This, in turn, can cause serious health issues, including increased blood sugar and diabetes, obesity, and high blood pressure to name just a few (Fakhlai et al., 2020). Consequently, honey represents a product that would strongly benefit from a highly transparent and immutable traceability system, which justifies the choice of honey as a product category under investigation in study 1.

We relied on two real-world (but rather less familiar) honey brands from a domestic supermarket chain as stimulus materials to account for any individual brand preferences and to increase the generalizability of the study’s results (see Fig. 2 for an example stimulus). In line with similar studies (Roosen et al., 2015), respondents were first introduced to the scope of the research by a slightly adapted real-world press release explaining the differences between the various labeling options, including the new blockchain technology, and referring to various food fraud scandals in different product categories (Radocchia, 2019).

Each product was presented in the online survey for exactly 15 s to ensure that the participants paid equal attention to the stimuli. The respondents were randomly allocated to one of the three experimental groups. In total, 151 individuals qualified for the final analysis (39% female, 58% male, 1% transgender, 2% prefer not to say; mean age: 27; highest education level: 61% university degree, 38% high school, 1% apprenticeship).

4.1.2. Measures

The questionnaire included items assessing the two constructs of perceived product quality and purchase intention. For both constructs, established and previously validated scales were used, which can be found in the appendix. The scales for measuring purchase intention and perceived product quality were taken from Dodds et al. (Dodds, Monroe, & Grewal, 1991). We further assessed package appeal with a single item— “the package design of this product is appealing”—to control whether the label in the blockchain-based traceability label condition led to differences in appeal as compared to the no-label condition. We further measured familiarity with the two brands used in order to guarantee that both brands have low levels of familiarity.

4.1.3. Assessing common method bias

In general, the reliance on the same scale formats for all constructs

Fig. 2. Stimulus material study 1.

might result in common method bias, leading to a systematic response behavior and causing artificial covariance (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, & Podsakoff, 2003). To reduce the risk of common method bias, we followed the recommendations from Futterer, Schmidt, and Heidenreich (2018) and conducted a pre-test to detect potential item ambiguity. Furthermore, we applied Herman's single-factor test with two constructs, namely product quality perceptions and purchase intention (Podsakoff et al., 2003). A comparison of the one-factor solution with the two-factor solution using a chi-square difference test resulted in a significantly worse model fit for the one factor solution ($\Delta\chi^2$ ($df = 1$) = 121.9, $p < .01$) while a confirmatory factor analysis with the two-factor model yielded a highly satisfactory fit (χ^2 ($df = 19$) = 25.60, RMSEA = .05, SRMR = .03, GFI = .96, NNFI = .99, CFI = .99). These results suggest that there is little threat from common method bias in our study.

4.1.4. Analysis and results

To test for the effectiveness of the manipulation, we asked respondents whether the product they had just seen included a label. A Chi-Square test confirmed that there was a significant association between the two experimental groups and label recognition (χ^2 (2, $N = 151$) = 74.42, $p < 0.01$). An ANOVA confirmed that a traceability label increases purchase intention ($F(1,149) = 12.58$, $p < 0.01$). The blockchain-based traceability label ($M_{BCLabel} = 4.41$, $SD = 1.76$) increased purchase intention as compared to the control condition ($M_{NoLabel} = 3.38$, $SD = 1.80$) (see Fig. 3). These results corroborate H1.

H2 postulates that perceived product quality mediates the influence of traceability labeling on purchase intention. This hypothesis was tested by estimating PROCESS model 4 with the experimental condition as the independent variable using 10,000 bootstrapping samples (Hayes, 2018). The dichotomous independent variable used the control condition as a reference category; therefore, coefficients report the increase in the mediator and dependent variable for the blockchain-based traceability label as compared to the no-label condition.

As hypothesized, a blockchain-based traceability label increases product quality perception ($a_1 = 0.50$, $p < 0.01$). The direct effect of traceability labeling on purchase intention is not significant when considering product quality perceptions as mediator ($c' = .01$, $p = 0.96$), whereas product quality perceptions significantly influence purchase intention ($b = 1.02$, $p < 0.01$). The indirect effect shows that perceived product quality fully mediates the influence of a blockchain-based traceability label on purchase intention ($a_1b = 0.51$, CI [.29, .73]). Hence, we can confirm H2 (see Table 1).

4.1.5. Study 1 discussion

The findings of study 1 corroborate a positive influence of traceability labeling on purchase intention as mediated by product quality perceptions. Traceability does not exert a direct effect on purchase intention, which indicates a full mediation through product quality perceptions.

Fig. 3. Differences in purchase intention between no label and a blockchain label.

4.2. Study 2 The moderating effect of brand familiarity

4.2.1. Design, procedure, and sample

While study 1 confirmed our theoretical reasoning on the positive effect of a blockchain-based label on purchase intentions as mediated by product quality perceptions, the results must be interpreted with caution since we employed a convenience sampling procedure. In order to enhance the generalizability of our findings, we followed the procedure suggested by Peterson and Merunka (2014) to test our theory in terms of the reproducibility and replication of results with another sample. Hence, study 2 was designed to validate the findings of study 1 (H1, H2) using a different food category as stimulus material, as well as further testing for the moderating effect of brand familiarity (H3). Salmon has previously been used as a stimulus in research that investigated the influence of organic labels on consumer choice (Larceneux et al., 2012) and has frequently been the subject of fraudulent food practices (Olmsted, 2015). Data from the RASFF (Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed) database, which is maintained by the European Commission, confirms that fish and seafood products represent the most reported food fraud incidents (Marvin et al., 2016). Therefore, we aimed to replicate the effects of study 1 and extend the model with the moderating variable of brand familiarity. The same stimulus material (i.e., product packaging) and procedure was used as in the previous study. In addition, we included a quick response (QR) label to rule out the alternative explanation that any additional information increases product quality perceptions. Similar to a blockchain label, a QR label can be considered as granting access to a traceability system, but it does not signal a specific kind of database or a specific kind of information quality. RFID or QR codes are technologies frequently deployed in traditional traceability systems and enable different actors along the supply chain to quickly and inexpensively store and access relevant information in a database. This information can be individually accessed by all participants of the supply chain (primary producers, processing industries, transport partners, end consumers) but is traditionally stored in a centralized database.

In order to test the moderating role of brand familiarity, in study 2 we used a 3 (traceability: no label vs. QR label vs. Blockchain label) \times 2 (brand familiarity: less familiar vs. familiar) full factorial between-subjects design. This design allowed us to not only test the causal relationship between the three different label types and purchase intention as well as the mediating role of product quality perceptions but also to assess a moderating effect of brand familiarity on this mediating effect. More specifically, this manipulation of brand familiarity fulfills the requirement according to Judd (2015) that "observations from all levels of the moderator occur at every level of the independent variable" and makes it possible to assess the causal effects of brand familiarity.

To manipulate brand familiarity, we used different brands of the same product (i.e., salmon). Manufacturer brands are often associated with higher quality as compared to private label brands (Ailawadi, Neslin, & Gedenk, 2001; Rubio, Oubiña, & Villaseñor, 2014) and are associated with higher levels of safety and value (Nenycz-Thiel & Romaniuk, 2009). Hence, manufacturer brands can be considered as well-established and stable brands with strong associations and favorable attitudes (Bettman & Sujun, 1987). In contrast, weak associations are characteristic of less familiar brands (Simonin & Ruth, 1998). The less familiar salmon brand was the private label of a domestic discounter (Ocean Sea). The Iglo salmon represented the familiar brand (see Fig. 4).

The acquisition of respondents and the experiment followed the same procedures as in study 1. Accordingly, students of a marketing research class sent out the questionnaire to consumers who regularly purchase salmon. The data was collected in May 2019. Each student recruited at least 25 respondents by forwarding the questionnaire link to family members, friends and colleagues.

In total, 152 respondents replied (45% female, 52% male, 3% transgender, 1% preferred not to say; mean age: 27; highest education: 50% university, 45% high school, 4% vocational school, 1%

Table 1
Relative direct and indirect effects for study 1.

Condition	Constructs				Y Purchase intention			
	M Quality perceptions				Relative direct effect			
	Coeff.	SE	p		Coeff.	SE	p	
Blockchain label	a_1	0.50	0.11		c'_1	0.01	0.10	.96
Quality perceptions (M)					b	1.02	0.07	.00
Constant	i_M	3.38	0.14	0.00	i_y	-0.58	0.30	.06
Relative indirect effect					a_1b	0.51	CI [0.29, 0.73]	
		$R^2 = 0.12$ F(1149) = 20.46, p < 0.01				$R^2 = 0.63$ F(2148) = 128.09 p < 0.01		

Fig. 4. Stimulus material study 2.

apprenticeship and compulsory school). Respondents were randomly allocated to one of the six experimental conditions. In addition to the measures used in study 1, the present study assesses brand familiarity using a semantic differential ranging from -3 to +3 (Simonin & Ruth, 1998).

4.2.2. Assessing common method bias

The same statistical procedure as in study 1 was applied to assess the

presence of common method variance. Again, Herman’s single factor test resulted in a significantly worse model fit ($\Delta\chi^2 (df = 1) = 143.74, p < .01$), while the measurement model with the two-factor solution yielded a highly satisfactory fit ($\chi^2 (df = 19) = 40.95, RMSEA = .08, SRMR = .03, GFI = .94, NNFI = .96, CFI = .98$). As another means to avoid common method bias, study 2 estimates a more complex model by accounting for the moderating role of brand familiarity. As Chang, van Witteloostuijn, and Eden (2010) point out, the inclusion of a moderating

variable “is likely to reduce CMV because such a complex relationship is, in all likelihood, not part of the respondents’ theory-in-use”.

4.2.3. Analysis and results

A Chi-Square test revealed that most participants correctly selected the appropriate label in the traceability labeling conditions and no label in the control condition. ($\chi^2(4, N = 151) = 229.87, p < 0.01$). Participants evaluated the Ocean Sea brand as significantly less familiar ($M = 0.15, SD = 1.75$) than the Iglo brand ($M = 1.46, SD = 1.73, F(1, 149) = 21.40, p < 0.01$). Hence, the manipulations for traceability label and brand familiarity worked as intended.

An ANOVA showed that the three conditions did not evoke different appeal evaluations ($F(2, 148) = .31, p = 0.31$). An ANCOVA with the traceability and familiarity conditions as factors and purchase intention as the dependent variable revealed a significant main effect of familiarity ($F(1, 145) = 11.98, p < 0.01$), a marginally significant main effect of traceability ($F(2, 145) = 11.98, p = 0.10$), and a marginally significant interaction effect of traceability \times familiarity ($F(2, 148) = 2.66, p = 0.07$). Contrast tests indicate that respondents had significantly lower purchase intentions in the familiar condition when the brand was promoted with a QR code label as compared to the control condition ($M_{noLabel} = 4.86, SD = 1.58$ vs. $M_{QRLabel} = 3.83, SD = 1.93, p = 0.04$). No significant difference was observed when comparing the no-label condition with the blockchain-based label condition ($M_{noLabel} = 4.86, SD = 1.58$ vs. $M_{BCLabel} = 4.67, SD = 1.82, p = 0.69$). In contrast, in the less familiar condition, the QR code label did not increase purchase intention as compared to the control condition ($M_{noLabel} = 3.14, SD = 1.31$ vs. $M_{QRLabel} = 3.49, SD = 1.18, p = 0.37$), while the blockchain label significantly increased purchase intention ($M_{noLabel} = 3.14, SD = 1.31$ vs. $M_{BCLabel} = 4.03, SD = 1.50, p = 0.03$). Hence, it seems that for familiar brands, a traceability label does not increase purchase intention, while less familiar brands can benefit from a blockchain label but not from a QR label. This result corroborates H3 (see Fig. 5).

To explore product quality perceptions as an underlying mechanism that explains these effects (H2 and H3), we estimated a multicategorical moderated mediation model (PROCESS v.3 Model 7 with 10,000 bootstrapping samples (Hayes, 2018)). This procedure requires a dummy coding for the experimental conditions wherein the control group serves as the reference category. Hence, the QR-label condition and the blockchain-based label condition are compared to the no-label condition. In contrast to mediation analysis with dichotomous or continuous variables, this implies that we obtain more than one direct and one indirect effect (Hayes, 2018). Due to the multicategorical nature of the independent variable, the set of regression coefficients increases, leading to the estimation of two relative direct effects (a, c') and two relative indirect effects (a_1b and a_2b) for each experimental condition (in comparison to the no-label condition) (see Table 2). Results reveal that the blockchain label increased product quality perceptions ($a_2 = 2.00, p < 0.01$), but the QR code label did not ($a_1 = 0.23, p = 0.74$) (see Table 2). Hence, not all labels are equally effective at increasing product quality perceptions and, in turn, purchase intentions. In support of H3, the analysis reveals a moderating effect of brand familiarity on the mediating effect of product quality perceptions on purchase intentions. The blockchain label increased purchase intention through product quality perceptions; however, this effect was only significant in the less familiar brand condition ($a_5b_{BC,U} = .12, CI[0.48, 1.78]$) as opposed to the

familiar brand condition ($a_5b_{BC,F} = .33, CI[-0.20, 0.80]$).²

4.2.4. Study 2 discussion

Combining the results from studies 1 and 2, we conclude that only in the less familiar brand condition does a blockchain-based label condition increase product quality perceptions as compared to a QR label condition or a no traceability labeling condition. Neither traceability condition directly influences purchase intention when considering product quality perceptions as a mediating construct. In combination with the lack of a direct effect of traceability on purchase intention, this points to a full mediation of perceived product quality on the effect of blockchain-based traceability labeling on purchase intention for less familiar brands, while such a mediating effect does not exist for the QR code tracking condition. In turn, and corroborating the findings of study 1, product quality perceptions significantly predict purchase intention.

In summary, the results of study 2 confirm the results from study 1, demonstrating that the conceptual model remains stable across product categories. Blockchain traceability labeling increases consumers’ purchase intentions via product quality perceptions. Additionally, we identified brand familiarity as a relevant boundary condition.

5. Discussion

Recent food scandals call for higher levels of information transparency along the supply chain. Referring to extant literature suggesting that blockchain’s features of immutability and shared data access contribute to information transparency (Rogerson & Parry, 2020), we investigate the influence of traceability systems on consumer perceptions of the quality of food products and how these perceptions, in turn, affect purchase intentions. Our research was guided by two questions, respectively investigating: “how traceability labels signaling the use of blockchain technology can impact consumers’ perceptions of product quality and their purchase intentions” (RQ1) and “what role brand familiarity plays in consumers’ perceptions of blockchain-enhanced product quality” (RQ2).

Two consecutive online experiments tested the research questions. Study 1 explored the extent to which a blockchain-based traceability label positively affects product quality perceptions, while study 2 investigated the extent to which a blockchain-based traceability label has superior effects on quality perceptions as compared to another traceability label (QR-code label). Further, we accounted for the moderating effect of brand familiarity in study 2.

Answering RQ1, the results of study 1 confirm our assumption that a blockchain-based traceability label increases perceived product quality, which positively impacts purchase intentions. Findings of study 2 validate this finding, as well as identifying brand familiarity as a boundary condition for the positive indirect effect of a blockchain-based label on purchase intention: for the familiar brand, the blockchain-based label did not affect product quality perceptions and, consequently, we did not observe any effect on purchase intention. We theorized that this result can be explained by a ceiling effect: Strong (familiar) brands already possess favorable brand associations, which hinder the acquisition of any new favorable associations (Janiszewski & Van Osselaer, 2000). Based on this result, blockchain-based traceability labels seem to be most efficient in terms of prompting favorable quality perceptions for less familiar, less strong brands. Study 2 further confirms the robustness

² The finding was replicated in a setting in which we considered measured (instead of manipulated) brand familiarity as a moderating variable in a moderated mediation analysis (model 7). We found that brand familiarity did not moderate the mediating effect of product quality perceptions on the impact of a QR label on purchase intention. For the blockchain label, a significant mediating effect was observed, which was strongest for the respondents who indicated low familiarity levels (.86, [.26, 1.61]) and less pronounced for respondents who indicated high familiarity levels (.58, [.11, 1.00]).

Fig. 5. Differences in purchase intention between the experimental conditions. (QR ... quick response; BC ... blockchain)

Table 2
Relative direct and indirect effects for study 2.

Model 1	Constructs												
	M Quality perceptions Relative direct effect				Y Purchase intention Relative direct effect			Y Purchase intention Conditional indirect effects			Index of moderated mediation		
Condition	Coeff.	SE	p		Coeff.	SE	p	Coeff.	SE	CI			
QR label	a_1	0.23	0.70	0.74	c'_1	-0.44	0.25	0.08	QR Label				
Blockchain label	a_2	2.00	0.68	0.00	c'_2	-0.42	0.25	0.09	$a_4 b_{QR,U}$	0.11	0.33	[-0.52, 0.76]	-0.11 [-0.97, 0.68]
Familiarity	a_3	1.21	0.30	0.00					$a_4 b_{QR,F}$	0.00	0.27	[-0.53, 0.53]	
QR x Familiarity	a_4	-0.11	0.43	0.79					Blockchain Label				
BC x Familiarity	a_5	-0.83	0.42	0.05					$a_5 b_{BC,U}$	1.12	0.33	[0.48, 1.78]	-0.79 [-1.68, -0.0]
Quality perceptions (M)				b	0.95	0.09	0.0		$a_5 b_{BC,F}$	0.33	0.25	[-0.20, 0.80]	
Constant	i_M	2.47	0.49	0.0	i_y	-0.04	0.42	0.93					
$R^2 = .23$				$R^2 = .47$									
$F(5145) = 8.82, p < 0.01$				$F(3147) = 42.76, p < 0.01$									

of the results gained by study 1 by including not only a no-label condition as control group, but also a QR-code label condition. For less familiar brands, the blockchain-based label was superior as compared to both alternative conditions.

The findings of our study extend previous research that postulates that blockchain can have a positive impact on transparency and traceability in supply chains. This research stream was established on a theoretical level by Treiblmaier (2018) and Montecchi et al. (2019) and, for the food industry, postulated by Yiannas (2018) as well as Hughes et al. (2019).

Furthermore, we illustrate the practical applicability of signaling theory to gain further insights into consumers' perceptions of blockchain technology, corroborating its effectiveness in a technology-related context (Connelly, 2016). On a global scale, blockchain can constitute an important driver for sustainable supply chain management, especially in developing countries (Kshetri, 2021), and our findings demonstrate how its positive impacts can be easily communicated to consumers.

5.1. Theoretical contributions and implications

Traceability has already attracted considerable research attention in information systems, supply chain, and food research journals, and previous research has identified numerous benefits, such as reductions in shrinkage and costs as well as improvements in efficiency and quality control (Aung & Chang, 2014; Chen & Huang, 2013). The improved traceability resulting from blockchain deployment has also been

identified as a means of addressing vaccine record fraud (Yong et al., 2020). However, only limited research has thus far investigated the consumer perspective on traceability systems. One notable exception stems from Yoo et al. (2015), who used a combination of principal agent theory and the technology acceptance model to highlight the importance of traceability for consumers' willingness to pay a premium and their purchase intentions.

In this paper, we close this theoretical research gap by investigating the role of food traceability from a signaling theory perspective. We argue that a traceability label represents an extrinsic cue that can be used to signal product quality for perishable food items. More specifically, we thoroughly investigate how a blockchain label can signal product quality relative to other traceability labels while considering brand familiarity as moderating this signaling effect. In the current research, signaling theory helps to understand how the conveyance of additional information can mitigate consumers' uncertainty toward perishable food items. A fast and reliable supply chain turns out to be particularly important for quality assurance. Importantly, we identify traceability systems as drivers of perceived product quality and consequently purchase intention. The integration of marketing and supply chain literature follows the call to offer interdisciplinary perspectives on innovative supply chain technologies and their applications (Kozlenkova, Hult, Lund, Mena, & Kecec, 2015; Treiblmaier, 2021).

These theoretical considerations guided the development of a model that offers in-depth knowledge pertaining to the influence of traceability systems on outcomes that are relevant for information systems researchers. Confirming prior research from Mavlanova et al. as well as Ou

and Chan (Mavlanova et al., 2012; Ou & Chan, 2014), we illustrate that consumers can use signals to differentiate between products. Across two studies, we identify and replicate the strong influence of traceability labels on purchase intentions. In this regard, we extend previous applications of signaling theory within the blockchain context (Chod, Trichakis, Tsoukalas, Aspegren, & Weber, 2020; Fisch, 2019) and confirm that the use of blockchain labels poses a signal to customers that elicits associations with the core attributes of blockchain such as immutability and traceability. This, in turn, increases purchasing intention and provides a new theoretical underpinning for researchers who are interested in perceptual antecedents of intentions and behavior.

Finally, the results offer several crucial boundary conditions pertaining to the positive effects of blockchain-based traceability information. Adaptive learning models build the foundation for proposing a ceiling effect when a familiar brand uses a blockchain label. We illustrate that only less familiar brands benefit from adding blockchain-based traceability information to increase perceived product quality and, consequently, purchase intention. Our results identify ceiling effects when simultaneously combining and presenting two strong cues, such as a well-known brand and a blockchain label. Having already achieved strong perceptions of product quality without adding any additional cue, familiar brands do not offer room for further perceptual improvements. Hence, no additional gain in product quality perception is possible for familiar brands. In contrast, fewer brand associations exist for less familiar brands, which enables adaptive learning in the presence of a blockchain label.

5.2. Implications for practice

The economic loss to the global food industry caused by food fraud is estimated to range between USD 30bn and USD 40bn per year (PwC, 2016). In order to remedy this situation, the EU, for example, has developed a legislative proposal for a new single market program for the period 2021–2027, in which the Commission proposes a total allocation of EUR 1.68 bn for food safety (European Commission, 2018). The resulting requirements for tracking food will also increase consumer awareness regarding the relevance and the requirements of traceability systems. According to Statista (2019), the value of the worldwide food traceability market will increase from USD 11.63bn in 2016 to USD 16.09bn in 2022.

One of the most promising scenarios for the application of blockchain technology is supply chain management, wherein the features of the technology can help to ensure product traceability by providing immutable, accessible, and up-to-date information for all parties who are authorized to access it. This represents a novel solution for a highly relevant problem: the traceability of food. Numerous academic and practitioner-oriented research studies have previously highlighted the importance of traceability to ensure food safety as well as consumer loyalty from a business perspective. Especially in cases where public health is at risk, the rapid spread of information across the supply chain is of paramount importance. Despite the significant role that consumers play within value chain networks, their perceptions of traceability information are currently under-researched and poorly understood. Extant research even notes that it is “unlikely that information provision about the technical aspects of traceability will boost consumer confidence” (Rijswijk & Frewer, 2008, p. 1036). Therefore, our study design briefly informed participants about the impact of blockchain technology on traceability and applied product labels to communicate the application of the technology in an easily understandable format for laypersons. As knowledge about blockchain becomes more widespread in the general public, companies will benefit from communicating the use of this technology without the need to offer additional information. Our contribution to the industry is threefold.

Firstly, we have summarized previous research indicating that traceability labeling can have a positive effect on consumers. This is especially true for labels that signal to consumers that blockchain

technology is used to reliably record food-related information. Labels are easy to attach to products and are already widespread practice in today’s retail business. Therefore, signaling the use of blockchain technology by using labels implies a rather small additional effort for organizations once a technological solution has been developed and implemented. It is only by informing the public, which can be done proactively by companies, that the benefits of blockchain are likely to be realized.

Secondly, we found that blockchain labels have a positive effect on purchase intention via perceived product quality. This stands in contrast to the effect of QR labels or no labels at all. This is vital information for companies who want to clearly communicate their efforts to ensure safe food supply chains. In order to gain credibility, they can also give consumers access to safety-relevant food information on the blockchain and thus allow them to take an active part in the supply chain. Companies can also implement policies that clearly specify the extent to which consumers should be informed about existing traceability systems.

Thirdly, brand managers can use blockchain to actively manage product quality perceptions for less familiar brands. This can help them to establish new brands more quickly or to gain credibility for existing but relatively unknown brands. Blockchain shifts the trustworthiness of information from individual persons or organizations to technology and, in the case of supply chain networks, to a group of organizations that share responsibility. Companies can easily exploit the manifold opportunities blockchain technology offers and use them to establish a positive brand perception in the minds of consumers. In this paper, we have not only demonstrated that the provision of blockchain-based traceability information results in benefits for (less familiar) retailers, but we have also outlined how these benefits can be easily communicated to consumers (i.e., in the form of product labels).

Finally, from a general perspective, our studies also provide important implications for policy makers and society at large. Given the benefits associated with a decentralized traceability system (as outlined in Section 2.2), policy makers might encourage retailers and manufacturers to rely on blockchain-based traceability systems to reduce health hazards for the public and to increase public welfare.

5.3. Limitations and future research directions

As is the case with every empirical study, our research has several limitations that point toward the need for future in-depth research and replication studies. Firstly, while we demonstrate the robustness of our conceptual model with two different samples, our findings are based on convenience samples; further studies are encouraged to use quota-sampling procedures to ensure that our results hold across different age groups and cultures.

Secondly, consumers still need to be educated on what they can expect from blockchain-based solutions, how to use and verify them, and what their limitations are. The latter is especially important in case companies start to collect and store consumers’ personal data on an immutable ledger. It appears likely that blockchain technology will mainly affect backend processes and in many cases might be invisible to end consumers. Although we do not expect the collection of private data to happen on a large scale in food traceability systems, compliance with regulatory frameworks might become an issue for various organizations in the supply chain. However, if implemented diligently, blockchain solutions might even support companies in fulfilling their regulatory requirements.

Thirdly, future research needs to focus on the presentation of blockchain-based traceability information that meets consumers’ informational needs. In this context, qualitative research conducted with focus groups might be a fruitful approach to investigate what information consumers actually require to be able to evaluate a product’s authenticity. Based on this knowledge, the development of user interfaces that efficiently communicate blockchain-based traceability information will foster the deployment of blockchain technology in

retailing and add value to the overall customer experience.

Fourthly, our stimuli selection for the two experimental studies included honey and salmon, two of the most frequently adulterated food products. We purposefully chose products that are fairly different from each other to create robust findings, but further studies are needed to confirm our findings across other product categories.

In summary, blockchain technology is at a budding stage and faces numerous adoption barriers (Mathivathanan, Mathiyazhagan, Rana, Khorana, & Dwivedi, 2021). Especially in food supply chains, important boundary conditions need to be overcome before blockchain can be successfully deployed (Behnke & Janssen, 2020). Additionally, the underlying technologies and protocols are under constant development. It is especially the combination with other technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), or the Internet of Things (IoT) that promises many interesting application, scenarios, and synergies (Dwivedi et al., 2021). For example, future supply chains might include numerous points of data collection which can be completed automatically during warehousing, manufacturing, and transportation operations (Rejeb, Keogh, & Treiblmaier, 2019). This would allow for the cost-efficient gathering of data that can be shared in real time with partners in the supply chain. If consumers are included in this process and allowed to access the food-related information that is relevant for them, this could be an important step toward further improvements in food safety.

6. Conclusions

Several important key points emerge from this study. Firstly, extant research highlights traceability as an important predictor for perceived food safety and quality and has explored the requirements and factors that need to be considered when integrating a traceability system. However, only limited research has examined the potential impact of traceability from a consumer perspective. The synthesis of information systems with supply chain and marketing literature thus generates new knowledge pertaining to the benefits of traceability systems from an interdisciplinary perspective.

Secondly, our study offers empirical evidence on the linkage between traceability labels and consumers' perceptions of product quality. Prior research has found that eco-labels have the potential to shape consumers' attitudes and traceability systems have been linked to quality assurance in the food sector on a theoretical level. However, no rigorous research study has yet tested the influence of different traceability systems on consumers' perceptions of quality and their purchase intentions. By comparing the impact of a blockchain-based traceability label with other labels, we provide new insights into the effectiveness of a transparent supply chain for shaping consumers' attitudes and intentions.

Thirdly, the findings of this research contribute to the ongoing debate on viable blockchain application opportunities. In this regard, we identify blockchain as a technology that has the potential to revolutionize food traceability by providing immutable, shared, and easily accessible information throughout the agri-food value chain. This leads to numerous challenges that are currently under-researched including the retail applicability of blockchain technology and its benefits from a consumer-centric perspective. Extant studies that refer to blockchain as a promising technology that will revolutionize food traceability have not empirically tested the influence of blockchain-based traceability information on consumer perceptions and responses. Therefore, we systematically explore the potential impact of blockchain in a retailing context from a consumer-centric perspective by using a rigorous theory-based approach that guides the execution of two experiments.

Finally, our research offers insights into the boundary conditions of blockchain traceability systems. The current study demonstrates that blockchain-based traceability information increases product quality perceptions for less familiar brands but not for familiar ones. Given the product quality perceptions already associated with familiar brands, the addition of a blockchain label does not further increase the positive

perceptions of those brands, which indicates a ceiling effect. Applied in practice, this suggests that especially marketers of less familiar brands should consider the advertising of blockchain-based traceability systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Horst Treiblmaier: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review. & editing. **Marion Garaus:** Data collection, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Appendix. – Measures

Dependent variable

Purchase Intention (Dodds et al., 1991), $\alpha_{\text{Study1}} = .95$, $\alpha_{\text{Study2}} = .95$
Seven-point Likert scale (very low – very high).

- The likelihood of me purchasing this product is...
- The probability that I would consider buying the product is...
- My willingness to buy the product is...

Mediator

Product quality perceptions (Dodds et al., 1991), $\alpha_{\text{Study1}} = 93$, $\alpha_{\text{Study2}} = 90$
Seven-point Likert scale (very low – very high).

- This product is likely to be reliable.
- This product appears to be of quality.
- This product appears to be durable.
- This product appears to be dependable.
- I view the product's brand name positively.

Moderator

Brand familiarity (Simonin & Ruth, 1998).
Semantic differential (–3 to +3).

- Unfamiliar/Familiar

Control variable

Package appeal (Seven-point Likert scale (very low – very high)).

- The package design of this product is appealing.

Manipulation check

Label awareness (answer categories: no, QR code label, blockchain label).

- Does the package include a label? If yes, please mark the label you have seen.

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